

Integrative Review on Use of NTISS as Disease Severity Index

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Abstract— In order to provide increasingly effective and quality care using adequate financial resources, patient severity measurement scales were developed and applied in intensive care units (ICU), but it was only validated in 1991 the Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System (NTISS). Thus, the objective is to discuss the NTISS and its applicability. This is an integrative review with a qualitative approach and exploratory character through nine articles. Of these, it was possible to observe that the years 2012 and 2014 had the highest number of publications. Most of the studies found were in a foreign language and published in the south and southeast regions by physicians, and a relevance of this score was also observed for the identification of accuracy, and the prognosis of preterm newborns. Note that the NTISS is a score that was developed with the aim of helping the provision of care, improving the quality of care and reducing hospital costs, through scores and dimensions through the observation of the procedures performed. The same is considered a good predictor for the evaluation of hospital mortality, in addition to enabling the analysis of the score through the evaluation of medical records. Despite being a recent score, since its adaptation took place in the 1990s, the need for updated knowledge and the search for improvement in the quality of care provided should be factors that guide care and, therefore, the NTISS should be better studied and implemented in inpatient units.

Keywords — Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, Technology Utilization Index, Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System.

I. INTRODUCTION

With globalization and technological evolution, the care provided in health units has been modified over the years, with methods that contribute to the assistance provided. In this way, the assistance provided in the neonatal intensive care units (NICU) was reorganized, and it can benefit from equipment and new knowledge that make it possible to minimize injuries and mortality in newborns. They also influence, in a positive way, the survival in premature newborns through quality care [1,2].

It is defined as premature or preterm, according to the World Health Organization [3], all those born with less than 37 weeks of gestation, being those that require a longer hospital stay and often occupy beds in NICUs due to its physical vulnerability and all the physiological systems, but mainly, immune and neurological and cutaneous-mucous barriers still in development. These patients are often submitted to invasive procedures to provide their full development, which requires increased demands related to the care provided, making the use of essential technological advances [4,5].

With the objective of providing an increase and effective quality care, and using adequate financial resources, capable methods of evaluating the clinical conditions of the patient,

as well as the adopted conducts are being used [2]. Due to this need that patient severity measurement scales were developed and applied in intensive care units (ICU), but it was only in 1991 that the Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System (NTISS) was validated [4,6].

In 2005, researchers from the United Kingdom evaluated the 12 existing scales for measuring the severity of diseases in newborns (NB), and found that among the existing ones, the NTISS can evaluate a greater number of variables, becoming a more efficient predictor [2,7]. The NTISS is a mean of measurements that was adapted from the Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System (TISS), which is a method of measuring disease-related injuries in adult patients admitted to ICUs and the workload of the nursing team [8,9].

Thus, the NTISS comprises 62 items, which include eight dimensions related to respiratory, cardiovascular, metabolic/nutritional function, monitoring performed on the patient, medications used by the same, procedures performed, transfusions and vascular access. This score provides a punctuation for the items in its dimensions. The calculation is based on the sum of the points in each item of each dimension, being one (1) the lowest value and four (4) the maximum value [2,4].

In addition, it makes possible to identify the use of resources, assists in providing clinical prognosis, and detects factors that can influence in the maintenance of the patient in a hospital environment, ensuring good accuracy and prognostic value to indicate the severity of the disease in newborns in need of care intensive. Therefore, its ability in the 24 hours after admission to predict mortality in term and preterm newborns is better evaluated [7,10].

Due to its effectiveness, several studies use the NTISS as a score to assess the accuracy in several aspects in preterm NBs hospitalized in NICUs [11-13]. For its proper use, the professional must have knowledge about the score, its dimensions, and the correct form of application. The authors of this study, working in a NICU, notes the need to disseminate information about this score and, because of that, reiterates her interest in the subject. Therefore, the aim of the study is to discuss the Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System (NTISS) and its applicability.

II. METHODOLOGY

This is an integrative review with a qualitative approach and exploratory character. It was used the PICO (patient, intervention, comparison, outcomes) strategy for the elaboration of the research question. This strategy makes it possible to formulate the research problem in conducting review methods, so that it is possible to identify keywords to facilitate the search for scientific articles in the databases. Thus, the delimited research question was: “What is the applicability of the Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System (NTISS)?”

The following databases were used to search for papers: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO), Online System of Search and Analysis of Medical Literature (MEDLINE) and Latin American and Caribbean Literature in Health Sciences (LILACS), through the Virtual Health Library (VHL), using the descriptors available in the Descriptors in Science and Health (DECs): Neonatal Intensive Care Unit; Technology Use Index; Neonatal Therapeutic Intervention Scoring System.

III. RESULTS

A total of 37 publications with the selected descriptors were found in the databases. With the removal of duplicate articles, 19 articles remained. After this step, the inclusion criteria were defined, and 14 articles were selected. Of the 14 eligible articles, 5 were excluded after reading their abstracts that were not close to the proposed objective. Thus, 09 articles were selected for this study. No studies were found through manual search in the references of the articles found.

Through the analysis, it was possible to observe that the years 2012 and 2014 had the highest number of publications, with two publications each. The other years (1992, 1995, 1998, 2006 and 2009) had one publication each. No recent publications were found that addressed the applicability of NTISS. Current studies address this score being applied to identify injuries or harm related to injuries and different injuries.

Most of the studies found were in a foreign language, 04 in English and 01 in Spanish, being observed a relevance of this score for the identification of the accuracy and the prognosis of preterm NB. However, a gap is still observed

regarding the interest and applicability of this score in NICUs in Brazil, since there are few national studies found and they do not address their regular use in these environments.

Regarding the methodological design of the articles, it is noteworthy that seven were original researches and only two were review articles, one being an integrative review article and one bibliographic review article. All the articles were published in journals.

It was observed that the number of publications in Brazil were concentrated in Southeast and South regions. Totalizing 03 works published in the South region and 01 in the Southeast region, being distributed among the states of the Rio de Janeiro (01), Rio Grande do Sul (02), and Paraná (01). The main academic schools that train professionals of excellence are concentrated in the Southeast region, making it a scientific center, in addition to the largest pilot health programs being present in this region.

Despite being a relevant score, and for the dimensioning of professionals of the nursing team, it is noted that most authors are doctors (21 professionals) and only 04 are nurses, reinforcing the need to disseminate information and interest on the subject for these health professionals, especially for the nursing team, since they are responsible for providing care.

“Table 1” presents the synthesis of the studies included in the review, which constituted the study corpus and represented the essence for the elaboration of the results, discussion, and respective conclusion about application of the NTISS score and ICUs.

TABLE I. ARTICLES SELECTED TO COMPOSE THE INTEGRATIVE REVIEW, CURITIBA BRAZIL. 2022

Author/ Year	State	Study Type	Results	Magazine
CURAN, ROSSETTO, 2014	PR	Descriptive observation	The easy-to-apply scoring system proved to be an important tool for planning the allocation of material and human resources in care, as it reveals a situational diagnosis of the context.	Online Brazilian Journal of Nursing
CANABARRO et al., 2009	RS	Integrative Review	The daily assessment of the 28 variables of the TISS allows obtaining an evolutionary profile of hospitalized children, which may help to understand the clinical worsening of the hospitalized child's condition and its prognosis.	Revista Ciência&Saúde
MENDES et al., 2006	RJ	Prospective study	The NTISS allowed the monitoring of care and proved to be an instrument capable of detecting variations in practices that can influence clinical results and operational costs.	Jornal de Pediatria
WU et al., 2014	Taiwan	Prospective study	The NTISS score at 48 hours had better predictive power than the NTISS score alone.	Pediatrics and Neonatology
FERRARA, 1998	Mar del Plata	Bibliographic Review	The NTISS is useful for studying resource consumption and assessing work styles, based on the estimation of the severity of the pathology treated according to the intensity of therapy received by the patient.	Rev. Hospital Matt. Inf. Ramon Sarda
BENICASA et al., 2012	RS	Prospective cohort study	SNAPPE II and NTISS scores, at least in the first week of hospitalization, are higher in patients who die, becoming predictors of mortality in this sample. NTISS remains high in conditions known to be serious during hospitalization.	Rev HCPA
GRAY et al., 1992	UK	Prospective study	NTISS is a valid measure of therapeutic intensity that is independent of birth weight and can be used as an indicator of neonatal disease severity and use of resources. Additional validation is required in other NICUs.	Pediatrics
OYGUR et al., 2012	Turkey	Prospective study	NTISS study using all parameters appears to be less predictive in EBP newborns.	Pediatrics International
GOEDHUIS et al., 1995	Holland	Prospective study	The NTISS score at admission is only correlated with mortality in newborns with birth weight < 1,500 g. There is no correlation with mortality in newborns with birth weight > or = 1,500 g, with gestational age, or with psychomotor development in the first year of life.	Ned Tijdschr Geneesk

*Source Author's own, 2022.

IV. DISCUSSION

NTISS is an efficient index for the knowledge of the use of technological resources and for the evaluation of the work developed by the team, being essential this adaptation according to the illness presented by the NB, as well as the treatment and therapy for the patient [2]. In addition to these benefits, it is important to emphasize that this score has a close association with hospital mortality [14]. However, it has little correlation with birth weight and gestational age, due to the fact that even using small intervals of weight variation, wide spectrums of severity are observed between pathologies [2].

Disease severity scales are valuable for assessing clinical outcomes and resource consumption in adult and pediatric intensive care, but they were less extensively developed for neonatal care and, therefore, the development and adaptation of the TISS for NTISS. There was little correlation with birth weight or gestational age, but scores were highly correlated with expected markers of disease severity, including mortality risk estimates by neonatal physicians, in-hospital mortality rates, and a measure of nursing acuity. Furthermore, when analyzing the day of admission, they were predictive of both the length of stay in the NICU and the total hospital expenses for survivors [15].

The non-use of certain items found in NTISS in the quantification of technologies used in two hospitals was described, one being particular and one public, comparatively [2]. In severity indexes, the included variables and their respective weights are extremely important. The balance between the number of variables and the ease of application makes it difficult to create a score that contemplates the need of all hospitals [6].

Certain variables not included as the use of albumin, more than a noninvasive ventilatory mode and the need to maintain more than one venous access in NB, were suggested [2]. The difference in hospital structure, medical conduct, complexity, and individuality of each patient justifies why certain parameters present in NTISS were not used and others should be included.

In his study carried out in Brazil [8], with the aim of evaluating the association of NTISS with mortality, presenting a sample of 129 newborns admitted to the NICU for 6 weeks, he obtained through the analysis of the score that during the first week of hospitalization, the scores present increased values in patients who progress to death, which can be considered as a predictor of mortality.

Other authors [2,10] consider that the NTISS is a tool that can be easily obtained through the analysis of medical records, in which it obtains the necessary data to complete this score. Although its accuracy is considered inferior because it does not use physiological data, contradictorily, it is an efficient instrument to measure the severity and is associated with the occurrence of nosocomial infection.

Although most of the articles found present the prospective study design [4,7,8,10,15,16], during the present review it was found that due to NTISS presenting variables that are part of the routine of care in the NICU, it can also be used in retrospective studies, with the advantage of conducting studies in a shorter time, and the opportunity to increase the number of sampling in small hospitals.

In a study [16] carried out in a NICU in Netherlands these findings were reinforced. In order to analyze the NTISS and its effectiveness as a prognostic indicator of mortality and psychomotor development in newborns admitted to an intensive care unit, it was found through the analysis of 152 medical records that 22 newborns died, with no significant correlation between the score NTISS and birth weight or gestational age. It was also seen that there is no correlation with mortality in newborns with birth weight $>$ or $=$ 1500g, with gestational age or with psychomotor development in the first year of life.

Other authors [7], by reviewing the medical records of 172 premature neonates who had a birth weight of $<$ 1500g, obtained as a result that 18 died within the first 7 days after birth. NTISS score at 48 hours was a better predictor of mortality than 24 hours after admission. Combining gestational age, birth weight, and NTISS score at 48 hours, birth weight contributes a little to the predictive power of mortality. The model with gestational age and NTISS score at 48 hours had better predictive power than the NTISS score alone.

However, in order to analyze and compare therapeutic methods, the severity of the disease must be previously established by means of another index based on physiological parameters, such as the SNAP (Score Neonatal Acute Physiology). The use of both indices, physiological severity, and therapeutic intensity, has been shown to be effective in research, both in pediatric and adult intensive care [14]. This occurs because the NTISS presents in its analysis items the quantification of procedures and therapies only to assess the severity of patients, not including the analysis of their clinical and physiological variables [4]. A score that presents accurate prognoses can bring numerous benefits to the neonatology area. Among these, the possibility of recognizing the factors of the unit that are directly related to the outcomes of hospitalizations, improving procedures, improving ethical decision-making, and evaluating the effectiveness of treatments versus costs [17].

In order to analyze the application of NTISS in a university hospital with 81 neonates followed up, it was observed that the mean NTISS score on different occasions was 23 at death, 17.2 at admission, 14.5 during hospitalization and 10.5 on high. When considering the analysis of each dimension, it was found that the highest scores were related to monitoring and medication. This knowledge is essential for the adequate allocation of professionals and material resources, adapting the assistance and care provided to the context in which the patient is inserted [2].

Despite the significance of the score in NICUs, it is emphasized that in developing countries, such as Brazil, not so many studies are found and the application of this score in order to identify associations of markers and indices of severity and possible injuries that may occur during hospital stay [5].

Despite this, it is reiterated about the use of this score in developing countries, since it presents a high complexity and diversity, as well as high costs related to hospitalization, situated at about US\$ 1,500 to US\$ 1,700 per day. The same points out that when dealing with developing countries, in which technologies are not always used properly, it is

necessary to make use of evaluations of practices, to “identify the elements that can later be the target of actions that aimed at improving care, whether from a clinical or administrative point of view” [4].

V. CONCLUSION

Note that NTISS is a score that was developed with the aim of helping to provide care to newborns, improving the quality of care and reducing hospital costs, by observing the dimensions of the procedures performed. The same is considered a good predictor for the evaluation of hospital mortality, in addition to enabling the analysis of the score through the evaluation of medical records, prospective and retrospective studies.

Since the analysis of the results of the use of NTISS indicator shows numerous applicability in the neonatal intensive care environment. Among them we list the comparison between private and public hospitals, mortality rates of services, evaluation of care delivery, use as a quality indicator, size the allocation of financial resources for technologies, and in the dimensioning of nursing professionals.

However, despite being a useful tool in developing countries, its use is still scarce due to the complexity of health and possible poor technological adequacy in these environments. The articles included in the review can be considered studies of easy reproduction, however few articles have been found, opportunistic an area to be developed. In addition, a limitation of Brazilian articles on the subject is also observed, reinforcing the limitation not only of the use of the score, but also of the dissemination of information about the NTISS.

Despite being a recent score, since its adaptation took place in the 1990s, the need for updated knowledge and the quest to improve the quality of care provided should be factors that guide care and, therefore, the NTISS should be better studied and implemented in the hospitalization units of NBs, mainly those of intensive care.

Future developments in this line of research include the expansion of the number of databases, the replication of studies in hospitals of different sizes, care, and locations.

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